

Three-component reaction of aldehydes, α -haloketones and benzoylacetonitrile and Michael addition of benzoylacetonitrile to chalcones both promoted by samarium triiodide : two routes for preparation of 1-benzoyl-1-cyano-2-aryl-3-aryloxypropane derivatives

Yun-Kui Liu^a, Yong-Min Zhang^{a,b*} and Zhi-Fang Li^a

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Zhejiang University (Campus Xixi), Hangzhou, 310028, P. R.China

E-mail : yminzhang@mail.hz.zj.cn Fax : 86-571-8807077

^bLaboratory of Organometallic Chemistry, Chinese Academy of Sciences, Shanghai, 200032, P. R.China

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Two methods are described for preparation of 1-benzoyl-1-cyano-2-aryl-3-aryloxypropane derivatives via three-component reaction of aldehydes, α -haloketones and benzoylacetonitrile or via Michael addition of benzoylacetonitrile to chalcones promoted by samarium triiodide.

Compared with the wide application of samarium(II) species in organic synthesis¹, less attention was paid to the application of samarium(III) species to that effect. However, the reports of using samarium(III) in mediating carbon-carbon bond formation reactions have gradually increased recently. For example, it has been reported² that α -haloketones could react with aldehydes to give α,β -unsaturated ketones promoted by SmI₃. Also mediated by SmI₃, β -diketones or β -ketoesters could condense with aldehydes to form benzylidene-substituted β -diketones or β -ketoesters³. Besides, catalyzed by SmI₃, tetrahydrofuran ring could be opened with acyl chlorides or acid anhydrides to yield 4-iodobutyl esters^{4,5}.

The art of performing efficient chemical transformation coupling three or more components in a single operation by a catalytic process avoiding stoichiometric toxic reagents, large amount of solvents and expensive purification technique, represents a fundamental target of the modern organic synthesis⁶. As a result, many reagents have been introduced for this purpose. For example, InCl₃^{6,7}, In(OTf)₃⁸, Yb(OTf)₃⁹, and BF₃•Et₂O¹⁰ etc. are amongst the most commonly used reagents. Recently, Shiraishi *et al.*¹¹ have reported that Sm^{III} species could mediate three-component coupling reaction of aldehydes, amines, and nitroalkanes to give pyrroles¹¹. Now we wish to report that SmI₃ could promote three-component reaction of aldehydes, α -haloketones and benzoylacetonitrile to give 1-benzoyl-1-cyano-2-aryl-3-aryloxypropane in moderate yields (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

Results and Discussion

When aromatic aldehydes **1** and α -haloketones **2** were treated with 1 equiv. SmI₃ for about 2 h at room temperature, almost all of the starting materials were consumed which indicated that the corresponding intermediate α,β -unsaturated ketones were readily prepared, then a solution of benzoylacetonitrile **3** was added to the mixture, giving 1-benzoyl-1-cyano-2-aryl-3-aryloxypropane derivatives **4** in moderate yields. The results are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Three-component coupling reaction promoted by SmI₃

Compd no	Ar ¹	Ar ²	Yield* %	M p (°C)
4a	Ph	Ph	63(70)	oil
b	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	Ph	65(68)	52-54
c	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	Ph	62(67)	49-51
d	4-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	Ph	58(62)	oil
e	3-BrC ₆ H ₄	Ph	62(67)	52-54
f	2,6-Cl ₂ C ₆ H ₃	Ph	60(65)	oil
g	Ph	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	64(69)	oil
h	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	66(72)	122-124
i	Ph	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	63(68)	56-58

*Figure in parenthesis is the yield of direct Michael addition of benzoylacetonitrile to the chalcone promoted by SmI₃

In our experiment, the reaction conditions were well studied. We found that the use of catalytic amount of SmI_2 (10%, 20% mol of SmI_2 based on aldehydes or α -haloketones) only gave lower yields of products, which indicated that use of stoichiometric amount of SmI_2 seemed necessary for the reaction. Aromatic aldehydes were suited for the reaction while aliphatic ones were unavailable. Moreover, the reaction of aldehydes, acetophenone with benzoylacetonitrile in the same conditions could not give the corresponding adducts.

According to our previous work², a possible mechanism of SmI_2 mediated three-component reaction of aldehydes, α -haloketones and benzoylacetonitrile is presented in Scheme 2.

As shown in Scheme 2, the reaction may firstly form intermediate **D**, then further Michael addition of benzoylacetonitrile to intermediate **D** affording the product **4** via **E** and **F**. Since SmI_2 was needed to activate both α -haloketones and benzoylacetonitrile, therefore, using stoichiometric amount of SmI_2 seemed reasonable. For comparison, direct Michael addition of benzoylacetonitrile to chalcones promoted by SmI_2 was also used to prepare 1-benzoyl-1-cyano-2-aryl-3-aryloxypropane derivatives. The results are also summarized in Table 1.

The Michael reaction is one of the most useful methods for the carbon-carbon bond formation and has wide synthetic application. Usually these reactions are carried out under a base condition, thus some side-reactions can not be avoided¹². The present procedure was carried out under neutral conditions, which may overcome these problems. Besides, the resulting products bearing aroyl and/or cyano groups may be potential useful intermediates in organic synthesis because both aroyl and cyano groups could be conducted a variety of transformations. Further studies on the utilization of products **4** are now in progress.

Experimental

Tetrahydrofuran was distilled from sodium-benzophenone prior to use. All reactions were conducted under a nitrogen-atmosphere. M.ps. were obtained on an electrothermal apparatus and are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu IR-408 spectrophotometer and ¹H NMR spect (CDCl₃) on a Bruker AC-400 (400 MHz) spectrometer, chemical shifts being expressed in ppm downfield from internal tetramethylsilane.

General procedure for three component reaction of aldehydes, α -haloketones and benzoylacetonitrile: To a pale yellow suspension of SmI_2 (1 mmol) in THF was added aldehyde **1** (1 mmol) and α -haloketones **2** (1 mmol) and stirred until **1** and **2** were almost consumed (monitored by TLC, about 2 h), then a solution of benzoylacetonitrile **3** (1 mmol) was added. The mixture was refluxed for 10–12 h, then water was added and the product was extracted with diethyl ether. The organic phase was collected, dried over Na_2SO_4 and evaporated to afford the crude product, which was purified by preparative TLC on silica gel using cyclohexane and ethyl acetate (5 : 1) as eluent : **4a** (Found : C, 81.45; H, 5.48; N, 3.89. $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{19}\text{NO}_2$ calcd. for : C, 81.56; H, 5.42; N, 3.96%); ν_{max} 2249 (CN), 1686 cm^{-1} (C=O); δ 3.46 (0.67H, dd, J_1 3.52, J_2 18.56 Hz, CH_2CO -isomer-1), 3.67 (0.33H, dd, J_1 3.52, J_2 18.56 Hz, CH_2CO -isomer-2), 3.77 (0.33H, dd, J_1 10.24, J_2 18.56 Hz, CH_2CO -isomer-2), 3.94 (0.67H, dd, J_1 10.24, J_2 18.56 Hz, CH_2CO -isomer-1), 4.14–4.18 (0.67H, m, CHCH_2H_b -isomer-1), 4.19–4.23 (0.33H, m, CHCH_2H_b -isomer-2), 4.79 (0.33H, d, J 4.80 Hz, CHCN -isomer-2), 5.36 (0.67H, d, J 4.80 Hz, CHCN -isomer-1), 7.13–8.12 (15H, m, ArH); m/z 353 (M^+); **4b** (Found : C, 74.46; H, 4.59; N, 3.70. $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{18}\text{ClNO}_2$ calcd. for : C, 74.32; H, 4.68; N, 3.61%); ν_{max} 2253 (CN), 1685 cm^{-1} (C=O); δ 3.43 (0.69H, dd, J_1 3.52, J_2 18.56 Hz, CH_2CO -isomer-1), 3.64 (0.31H, dd, J_1 3.52, J_2 18.56

Scheme 2

Hz, CH_aCO-isomer-2), 3.71 (0.31H, dd, J_1 10.24, J_2 18.56 Hz, CH_bCO-isomer-2), 3.87 (0.69H, dd, J_1 10.24, J_2 18.56 Hz, CH_bCO-isomer-1), 4.12–4.16 (0.69H, m, CHCH_aH_b-isomer-1), 4.18–4.20 (0.31H, m, CHCH_aH_b-isomer-2), 4.79 (0.31H, d, J 4.80 Hz, CHCN-isomer-2), 5.34 (0.69H, d, J 4.80 Hz, CHCN-isomer-1), 7.05–8.10 (14H, m, ArH); m/z 389 (M⁺+2), 387 (M⁺); **4c** (Found : C, 81.58; H, 5.68; N, 3.89. C₂₅H₂₁NO₂ calcd. for : C, 81.72; H, 5.76; N, 3.81%); ν_{\max} 2253 (CN), 1685 cm⁻¹ (C=O); δ 2.25 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.42 (0.65H, dd, J_1 3.52, J_2 18.56 Hz, CH_aCO-isomer-1), 3.63 (0.35H, dd, J_1 3.52, J_2 18.56 Hz, CH_aCO-isomer-2), 3.74 (0.35H, dd, J_1 10.24, J_2 18.56 Hz, CH_bCO-isomer-2), 3.92 (0.65H, dd, J_1 10.24, J_2 18.56 Hz, CH_bCO-isomer-1), 4.13–4.17 (0.65H, m, CHCH_aH_b-isomer-1), 4.18–4.21 (0.35H, m, CHCH_aH_b-isomer-2), 4.78 (0.35H, d, J 4.80 Hz, CHCN-isomer-2), 5.34 (0.65H, d, J 4.80 Hz, CHCN-isomer-1), 7.01–8.12 (14H, m, ArH); m/z 367 (M⁺); **4d** (Found : C, 78.47; H, 5.45; N, 3.74. C₂₅H₂₁NO₃ calcd. for : C, 78.31; H, 5.52; N, 3.65%); ν_{\max} 2251 (CN), 1686 cm⁻¹ (C=O); δ 3.42 (0.69H, dd, J_1 3.52, J_2 18.56 Hz, CH_aCO-isomer-1), 3.62 (0.31H, dd, J_1 3.52, J_2 18.56 Hz, CH_aCO-isomer-2), 3.71–3.77 (0.31H+3H, m, CH_bCO-isomer-2, CH₃O), 3.86 (0.69H, dd, J_1 10.24, 18.56 Hz, CH_bCO-isomer-1), 4.08–4.12 (0.69H, m, CHCH_aH_b-isomer-1), 4.13–4.16 (0.31H, m, CHCH_aH_b-isomer-2), 4.78 (0.31H, d, J 4.80 Hz, CHCN-isomer-2), 5.34 (0.69H, d, J 4.80 Hz, CHCN-isomer-1), 6.77–8.14 (14H, m, ArH); m/z 383 (M⁺); **4e** (Found : C, 66.56; H, 4.28; N, 3.29. C₂₄H₁₈BrNO₂ calcd. for : C, 66.68; H, 4.20; N, 3.24%); ν_{\max} 2253 (CN), 1685 cm⁻¹ (C=O); δ 3.44 (0.65H, dd, J_1 3.52, J_2 18.56 Hz, CH_aCO-isomer-1), 3.66 (0.35H, dd, J_1 3.52, J_2 18.56 Hz, CH_aCO-isomer-2), 3.72 (0.35H, dd, J_1 10.24, J_2 18.56 Hz, CH_bCO-isomer-2), 3.88 (0.65H, dd, J_1 10.24, J_2 18.56 Hz, CH_bCO-isomer-1), 4.09–4.12 (0.65H, m, CHCH_aH_b-isomer-1), 4.14–4.18 (0.35H, m, CHCH_aH_b-isomer-2), 4.78 (0.35H, d, J 4.80 Hz, CHCN-isomer-2), 5.32 (0.65H, d, J 4.80 Hz, CHCN-isomer-1), 7.11–8.10 (14H, m, ArH); m/z 433 (M⁺+2), 431 (M⁺); **4f** (Found : C, 68.13; H, 4.13; N, 3.40. C₂₄H₁₇Cl₂NO₂ calcd. for : C, 68.26; H, 4.06; N, 3.32%); ν_{\max} 2254 (CN), 1692 cm⁻¹ (C=O); δ 3.40 (0.54H, dd, J_1 3.52, J_2 18.56 Hz, CH_aCO-isomer-1), 3.89–3.96 (0.46H+0.46H, m, CH_aCO-isomer-2, CH_bCO-isomer-2), 4.14 (0.54H, dd, J_1 10.24, J_2 18.56 Hz, CH_bCO-isomer-1), 5.28–5.45 (2H, m, CHCH_aH_b-isomer-1, CHCH_aH_b-isomer-2, CHCN-isomer-2, CHCN-isomer-1), 6.96–8.11 (13H, m, ArH); m/z 421 (M⁺); **4g** (Found : C, 81.57; H, 5.66; N, 3.89. C₂₅H₂₁NO₂ calcd. for : C, 81.72; H, 5.76; N, 3.81%); ν_{\max} 2253 (CN), 1678 cm⁻¹ (C=O); δ 2.36 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.39 (0.67H, dd, J_1 3.52, J_2 18.56 Hz, CH_aCO-isomer-1), 3.62 (0.33H, dd,

J_1 3.52, J_2 18.56 Hz, CH_aCO-isomer-2), 3.74 (0.33H, dd, J_1 10.24, J_2 18.56 Hz, CH_bCO-isomer-2), 3.89 (0.67H, dd, J_1 10.24, J_2 18.56 Hz, CH_bCO-isomer-1), 4.12–4.16 (0.67H, m, CHCH_aH_b-isomer-1), 4.18–4.21 (0.33H, m, CHCH_aH_b-isomer-2), 4.80 (0.33H, d, J 4.80 Hz, CHCN-isomer-2), 5.36 (0.67H, d, J 4.80 Hz, CHCN-isomer-1), 6.81–8.12 (14H, m, ArH); m/z 367 (M⁺); **4h** (Found : C, 74.88; H, 5.13; N, 3.41. C₂₅H₂₀ClNO₂ calcd. for : C, 74.72; H, 5.02; N, 3.49%); ν_{\max} 2253 (CN), 1683 cm⁻¹ (C=O); δ 2.38 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.37 (0.71H, dd, J_1 3.52, J_2 18.56 Hz, CH_aCO-isomer-1), 3.61 (0.29H, dd, J_1 3.52, J_2 18.56 Hz, CH_aCO-isomer-2), 3.69 (0.29H, dd, J_1 10.24, J_2 18.56 Hz, CH_bCO-isomer-2), 3.86 (0.71H, dd, J_1 10.24, J_2 18.56 Hz, CH_bCO-isomer-1), 4.11–4.15 (0.71H, m, CHCH_aH_b-isomer-1), 4.16–4.19 (0.29H, m, CHCH_aH_b-isomer-2), 4.78 (0.29H, d, J 4.80 Hz, CHCN-isomer-2), 5.34 (0.71H, d, J 4.80 Hz, CHCN-isomer-1), 7.05–8.11 (13H, m, ArH); m/z 403 (M⁺+2), 401 (M⁺); **4i** (Found : C, 74.44; H, 4.76; N, 3.54. C₂₄H₁₈ClNO₂ calcd. for : C, 74.32; H, 4.68; N, 3.61%); ν_{\max} 2252 (CN), 1687 cm⁻¹ (C=O); δ 3.44 (0.63H, dd, J_1 3.52, J_2 18.56 Hz, CH_aCO-isomer-1), 3.63 (0.37H, dd, J_1 3.52, J_2 18.56 Hz, CH_aCO-isomer-2), 3.71 (0.37H, dd, J_1 10.24, J_2 18.56 Hz, CH_bCO-isomer-2), 3.87 (0.63H, dd, J_1 10.24, J_2 18.56 Hz, CH_bCO-isomer-1), 4.11–4.15 (0.63H, m, CHCH_aH_b-isomer-1), 4.19–4.21 (0.37H, m, CHCH_aH_b-isomer-2), 4.79 (0.37H, d, J 4.80 Hz, CHCN-isomer-2), 5.33 (0.63H, d, J 4.80 Hz, CHCN-isomer-1), 7.11–8.08 (14H, m, ArH); m/z 389 (M⁺+2), 387 (M⁺).

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